

EFFECT OF AGING ON AQUEOUS CORROSION BEHAVIOR OF SiC PARTICLE REINFORCED AL BASE MMCS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the influence of aging A356, AA6063, AA2014 and their SiC particle reinforced composites (10 vol %), which were prepared by the melt stirring process ,on their aqueous corrosion behavior. Electrochemical measurements and immersion tests in 3.5 % NaCl were carried out. The Brinell hardness of AA2014 / SiC and A356 / SiC composites were lower than that of the corresponding monolithic alloys aged to the same extent. This was due to preferential precipitation of intermetallics near the interfacial regions in the composites.. The composites corroded at a higher rate than the alloys and pitting was the major form of corrosion. The corrosion rates of the composites increased with aging times and the SiC / matrix regions with the high concentration of precipitates were the preferred sites for pitting.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) have attracted increasing attention in recent years because of their superior mechanical properties and low cost. They are predicted to have extensive applications in aerospace automotive and sports goods industries. Presently, a significant amount of data is available about the mechanical properties and correlations between processing route, microstructure and properties of MMCs. More information concerning their corrosion behavior is needed. This aspect is closely associated with the presence of heterogeneities, and MMCs have a large quantity of heterogeneities in the form of reinforcement, microcrevices, voids, porosity, intermetallic precipitates and interaction products. The aluminium alloy / SiC. composites can be produced by a variety of techniques and although the powder metallurgy route has been used quite extensively, the molten metal route is considered to be cost effective for large scale production.

Corrosion studies on Al composites in NaCl have shown localized corrosion to take place and to be controlled by alloy and reinforcement parameters.[1-5]. Paciej and Agarwala reported that factors which effect precipitation behavior, enhance corrosion resistance.[6]. The precipitation kinetics in composites of age hardenable Al alloys have been reported to be different from that in the unreinforced matrix alloys and the precipitation of certain phases is accelerated in the presence of the reinforcement[7] The precipitation behavior of heat treatable alloys has been reported

to alter the pitting susceptibility in the presence of SiC[8,9]. It has also been shown that changes taking place at the matrix / reinforcement interface effect mechanical behavior of MMCs [10]. These changes are due to a combination of one or more of the following: matrix alloy, particle surface characteristics, processing route and aging. The interfacial changes are usually in the form of variations in local composition, formation of precipitates, or other reaction products, and these effect corrosion behavior. This paper describes the effects of matrix alloy composition and aging on the corrosion behavior of Al / SiC composites.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Alloys A356 (Al-7.5Si-0.5Mg), AA2014 (Al-4.5Cu-1Si-0.8Mn-0.5Mg) and AA6063 (Al-0.5Si-0.8Mg) were used for preparing the composites. The procedure for the preparation of the composites consisted of adding 10 vol % of preheated particles of SiC (average size 50 μ m) to a vigorously stirred molten alloy bath. The agitation was carried out for 10 minutes prior to pouring the composites into chilled copper molds. The composite processing parameters such as melt temperature, stirrer design, stirring rate and duration, which affect reinforcement distribution were maintained at their optimized values to obtain uniform particle distribution[11]. Alloy and composite specimens were solubilized at 500°C for 1.5 h followed by quenching in water and then aged at 190°C for 2-14 h. The solubilized specimens were held in liquid nitrogen prior to aging. Age hardness of the various specimens was evaluated using Brinell macrohardness measurements. Microhardness measurements were not carried out as they were prone to be erroneous due to the possibility of making indentations in the matrix just above the SiC particle.

The corrosion measurements consisted of (a) anodic potentiodynamic polarization in 3.5% NaCl and (b) immersion tests in 3.5% NaCl at 25°C for 28 days. Specimens for the electrochemical measurements were cut to size (5x5x3mm), mounted in epoxy,ground to 600 grit,rinsed and introduced into a standard corrosion cell. The specimens were allowed to equilibrate prior to measurement of their corrosion potential E_{corr} and initiation of anodic scans from -1400mV to +100mV at 10mV/ s. The potential vs current curves were recorded. Measurements were carried out in both aerated and deaerated NaCl. Deaeration was achieved by bubbling nitrogen through the electrolyte before and during measurements. Specimens (10x10x3mm) for the immersion tests were prepared by grinding to 600 grit, degreasing and rinsing. The specimens were suspended in 3.5% NaCl, maintained at 25°C and pH 7. After the test, the specimens were cleaned in 50 vol % HNO₃, dried and weighed. The weight loss due to corrosion of the matrix and particle dropout were determined. A series of parallel experiments were carried out with the matrix alloy and some composites to determine the average weight loss due to particle dropout. In these experiments, small beakers were positioned within the testing tank of NaCl to collect the dislodged particles. At the end of the test, the specimens were cleaned with 10% HNO₃ and rinsed in a manner to permit the particles and the corrosion products to be collected. The solution containing the particles and corrosion products were filtered, and the weight of the residue determined. The overall percent contribution of the reinforcement and intermetallic precipitates in the residue weight was found to be 20-40%. Specimens from the immersion measurements and those exposed to 3.5% NaCl at 30mV above E_p were examined in a scanning electron microscope with analytical facilities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MICROSTRUCTURE AND HARDNESS

The as cast microstructures of alloy A356 and its composites revealed primary dendrites, eutectic silicon and the reinforcement. (fig 1). Alloy AA2014 revealed intergranular CuAl_2 distributed throughout as shown in fig 2., and Alloy AA6063 a fine distribution of nearly rounded Mg_2Si .

Figure 1. Optical micrograph of A356 / SiC composite.

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrograph of alloy AA2014.

The microstructures of the composites revealed the above mentioned features for the different alloys, and a fair distribution of SiC particles. Although significant improvements in particle distribution were achieved by controlling the composite processing parameters, particle clustering could not be completely eliminated.

The Brinell hardness of the alloys and the composite specimens in the solubilized as well as aged conditions are shown in Table 1. In general the hardness of the alloys and the composites increased

Table 1. Brinell hardness of the alloys and composites in as solubilized state and aged at 190 C

Aging time hours	Brinell Hardness					
	AA2014		A356		AA6063	
	Alloy	Composite	Alloy	Composite	Alloy	Composite
Solubilized	81.3	69.0	61.0	51.0	35.3	43.2
2	122.8	116.6	91.2	85.4	44.1	66.1
4	126.8	111.2	96.6	95.4	60.2	60.0
6	130.4	124.0	89.0	87.0	58.6	62.2
8	125.2	117.0	91.0	89.2	57.4	58.0
10	133.0	125.8	90.0	90.2	60.2	59.6
12	118.0	121.6	83.8	69.3	55.5	64.0
14	123.0	107.0	83.6	88.0	62.0	60.3

with aging times upto 10h and thereafter decreased. The hardness of AA2014 / SiC and A356 / SiC composites were lower than that of the corresponding alloys aged to the same extent. This was probably due to the regions in the composite specimens where the hardness measurements were made, having a significantly lower concentration of intermetallic precipitates, as compared to that in the alloy. It is well known that intermetallic precipitates form during aging at dislocations, voids and grain boundaries.[12,13] In composites, because of the differences in the coefficient of thermal expansion between the matrix alloy and the reinforcement, the regions of the matrix close to the particles have a high density of dislocations and are therefore the preferred sites for intermetallic precipitate nucleation upon aging The hardness of AA6063 / SiC composites on the other hand did not differ significantly from that of the alloy. This could be attributed to the lower alloying element content of this alloy as compared to that of the other two alloys.

CORROSION BEHAVIOR

The anodic polarization curves of the alloys and their composites were found to be similar and fig.3 shows a typical curve in 3.5% NaCl. In deaerated NaCl, E_p of the alloy and composites were 300-500mV higher than their corresponding E_{corr} . Upon aeration of the electrolyte, the difference between E_p and E_{corr} reduced to approximately 100mV, due mainly to increase of E_{corr} [1,4]. Table 2 lists the E_{corr} and E_p of the three alloys and their composites in aerated NaCl. The E_{corr} of AA2014 and its composite are higher than those of alloys A356, AA6063 and their composites. This is due to the presence of Cu in AA2014 [14]. The addition of SiC particles did not alter significantly the E_{corr} in NaCl. These observations differ from those reported elsewhere [15,16] wherein upon addition of SiC, the corrosion potentials became more active.

Immersion Test Results

The corrosion weight loss of the alloy and the composite specimens in the solubilized and aged conditions after 28 days immersion in 3.5% NaCl are given in Table 3. In general, weight loss of the composites were higher than those of the corresponding alloys. This increased corrosion weight loss is due to increased corrosion of the composite and to particle dropout. The overall corrosion rate of the alloys and the composites increased with aging times. McIntyre reported similar increase in corrosion rate with aging of alloy AA2014 and its composite [8]. In this alloy, as in other age hardenable alloys, during aging, intermetallic precipitates form and these increase in size with aging times. Since $CuAl_2$ is electrochemically cathodic to the matrix, they provoke

accelerated corrosion of the nearby matrix. In the other alloys, eutectic Si or other reaction products are the cathodic sites and Mg_2Si , an anode or a cathode depending on the composition of the surrounding matrix. In aged SiC particle containing composites, precipitation of intermetallics takes place preferentially near the reinforcement, and results in corrosion of the interfacial regions, leading to particle dropout.

Figure 3. Typical anodic potentiodynamic polarization curve of A356 in aerated 3.5% NaCl.

Table 2. Corrosion and pitting potentials of the alloy and composite specimens in aerated 3.5% NaCl at 25°C (vs SCE)

Alloy / Composite	E_{corr} (mV)	E_p (mV)
A356	-760	-620
A356 / SiC	-759	-600
AA2014	-690	-575
AA2014 / SiC	-700	-590
AA6063	-730	-700
AA6063 / SiC	-723	-690

Table 3. Corrosion weight loss of the aged alloy and composite specimens in 3.5% NaCl .

Aging time hours	Corrosion weight loss (mdd)					
	A356		AA2014		AA6063	
	Alloy	Composite	Alloy	Composite	Alloy	Composite
2	4.41	4.72	6.10	6.51	1.08	4.20
4	4.71	4.97	6.59	6.32	1.13	3.93
6	4.86	5.48	5.92	6.71	2.44	11.2
8	5.01	4.81	6.91	6.91	3.76	11.13
10	5.28	4.37	5.78	6.32	3.82	11.39
12	5.17	5.77	5.90	7.08	4.04	13.29
14	4.72	6.26	6.16	7.32	4.01	10.66

It has been reported elsewhere that in AA6061 / SiC composites, the aging kinetics increases with particle addition, whereas in A356 / SiC composites, the aging kinetics are ambiguous with particle addition[17,18]. In this investigation, similar trends were observed upon comparison of the corrosion weight loss of the alloys and the composites. Eventhough no significant increase in hardness was observed upon particle addition to AA6063, the composites of this alloy revealed a marked increase in corrosion weight loss as compared to the monolithic alloys. This could be attributed to particle drop out .The results of the parallel experiments mentioned earlier revealed that the percent weight loss due to particle dropout varied from 20-40%, depending on factors which include alloy grain size,particle content , size and distribution in the composite as well as intermetallic precipitates in the alloy. Investigations are being carried out to correlate these factors to particle dropout.

Pit Morphology

Alloy and composite specimens exposed at a fixed potential revealed both sporadic pits and pit clusters. At higher magnifications, crystallographic faceting was observed as shown in fig. 4a.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Scanning electron micrographs of A356 composites exposed to 3.5% NaCl.

The pits were deep, contrary to observations made elsewhere[1,19]. In the as cast A356 and AA6063 alloys exposed for 28 days to NaCl the pits eventhough few, were deep and crystallographic around inclusions. The matrix close to the eutectic Si were smooth and dimpled as shown in fig.4. In AA2014, the corrosion initiated in the matrix adjacent to the more noble CuAl_2 . (fig 2) In the composites, corrosion was predominantly around the SiC particles leading to particle dropout as shown in fig. 4b.

GENERAL DISCUSSIONS

In chloride ion containing solutions Al alloys generally pit. These pits initiate at surface oxide flaws which correspond to heterogeneities on the metallic surface. In the cast alloy or composite, these heterogeneities include: (a) casting defects,(b) silicon carbide, © SiC / matrix reaction products and (d) intermetallic precipitates formed during aging. The amount of intermetallic precipitates in the composites are significantly higher than in the unreinforced alloy subjected to similar treatments. Consequently, candidate sites for pit nucleation in the composites are higher. The main driving force for the corrosion reaction is the cathodic oxygen reduction reaction. The cathodic sites are the eutectic Si, and interaction products in the Si containing alloys and CuAl_2 in AA2014. In the composites, besides the above mentioned constituents, the SiC particles and the particle / matrix alloy reaction products also act as the cathodic sites. The Mg_2Si precipitates are themselves prone to dissolution depending on the matrix composition. Pit initiation involves Cl^- absorption at the flaws in the surface oxide film followed by chemical reaction [20]. During pit propagation, the heterogeneities in the alloy or composite play the main role.

The presence of a very large number of intermetallic precipitates such as CuAl_2 or Mg_2Si , and the mostly more noble eutectic Si and SiC in the aged composites cause extensive pitting of the matrix in chloride ion containing solutions. Also since a significant amount of the precipitates are formed close to the reinforcement, the matrix around the SiC dissolves and leads to particle dropout. Increase in aging time causes an increase in the number of precipitates and consequently results in increased corrosion. The differences in the corrosion rates of the composites of the different alloys aged to the same extent are due to differences in the electrochemical properties of the precipitates and their location.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The Brinell hardness of the composites AA2014 / SiC and A356 / SiC were lower than those of the corresponding monolithic alloys aged to the same extent, indicating preferential precipitation of intermetallics near the interfacial regions in the composites.
2. The hardness of alloy AA6063 and composite AA6063 / SiC did not vary as much as the other alloys, due probably to the lower alloying element content of this alloy.
3. The hardness of the alloys and the composites increased upon aging upto 10h and thereafter decreased.
4. In NaCl solutions, the pitting potential of the alloys and the composites were not affected by aeration of the solution. E_p of the composites were higher than those of the alloys.
5. Pit initiation sites in the composites were higher than in the alloys. The particle / matrix and precipitate / matrix regions were preferred sites for pitting and dissolution.
6. The oxygen reduction reaction is the driving force for the corrosion process and SiC particles, eutectic Si and precipitated phases are the cathodic sites.
7. The pits were crystallographic in nature and preferential pitting around SiC particles lead to particle dropout.

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